

USE OF INTERACTIVE METHODS IN PEDAGOGICAL EDUCATION

Erjanova Saboxon Bakhtiyorovna

Teacher of the Department of Preschool Education Methods, Faculty
of Pedagogy, UrSU

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6360116>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 17th february 2022

Accepted: 22th february 2022

Online: 27th february 2022

KEY WORDS

*interactive method,
pedagogical education,
effectiveness, method,
institution, teacher, student,
competence.*

ABSTRACT

In today's system of continuing education, teaching with modern pedagogical interactive methods creates the basis for students to learn more deeply and more solidly the subject being studied. The degree to which the educator can use these methods is also important. In this article, which covers similar issues, you can get acquainted with some of the interactive methods and learn in detail in what order you can use these methods during the lesson.

The choice of interactive teaching methods takes into account the purpose of education, the number and capabilities of students, the educational and material conditions of educational institutions, the duration of education, the pedagogical skills of the teacher, etc.

The use of interactive methods in the classroom serves to develop students' communicative competence.

What is communicative competence?

Communicative competence means the ability to communicate in social situations in the native language and in any foreign language, to adhere to the culture of communication in communication, to form social flexibility, the ability to work effectively in a team.

Interactive is derived from the English word Interactive, which means interaction and is explained in

pedagogical dictionaries. An interactive method is one in which an activity or problem is solved in a collaborative, participatory, participatory way. The advantage of this method is that the whole activity teaches the student to think independently and prepares them for independent living.

Here are some of these interactive methods:

1. BRAINSTORMING

Nowadays, various methods are being developed to increase the F.I.K of the brain condition. However, according to experts, we use only 7% of our brain. Educational methods that activate brain activity include social psychological training, synthetics, autogenic exercise, morphological analysis, role-playing, brainstorming and so on.

Brainstorming is derived from the English word and is one of the methods of

active learning management and research. This method monitors mental activity, develops creative and innovative intensity. The "Brainstorming" method, which is a stimulator of creative activity and productivity, is mainly based on a psychological mechanism called the absence of a critical environment that resists the birth of new, original ideas. In such an environment, any opinion isn't criticized, there is no fear to express and say false thought. The people, used brainstorming activities, ask them what they think about solving a particular problem and how they can come up with the most unexpected ideas. The person conducting the method writes down all the ideas. At this point, he does not express a critical opinion on the point being made, and the thought can be written to the end.

The purposes of the "brainstorming" method are:

- come up with ideas to solve the problem;
- sorting ideas according to their importance;
- formation of active thinking skills;
- demonstrate the process of emergence of unexpected ideas;
- develop the ability to use the ideas found;

It is argued in creative psychology that critical thinking slows down the process of developing ideas. Even the strongest ideas fail to resist both the generator and the critics. Therefore, the following rules apply to "brainstorming":

1. Criticism (even humor) is forbidden at the stage of advancing ideas.
2. Original, even fantastic ideas are encouraged.

3. All ideas are recorded, or recorded on audio or video film.

4. If it is approved, the author can write it oneself.

5. All participants of the method of "brainstorming" should not be legally and administratively (administratively) interconnected.

6. A team of analysts analyzes, synthesizes, evaluates, and selects relatively effective ideas

The "brainstorming" method can be performed in different ways:

- verbal individual expression. In this case, the author and his idea are inevitably recorded on the blackboard;

- The method of "brainstorming" can also be implemented in the form of "Conference of Ideas";

- In another form of "brainstorming" the author himself writes down his thoughts and explains them orally;

It is well known that in some work-related games, "brainstorming" is used during the discussion of certain issues. Therefore, educators need to master the technology of applying the method of "brainstorming" in the game process as perfectly as possible.

2. "CLUSTER" METHOD

The cluster method is a specific form of pedagogical, didactic strategy that helps students to express themselves openly and freely on voluntary problems. This method provides an opportunity to think about the connections between different ideas and the defining structure is required to be determined. The "cluster" method is a form of thinking that is not focused on a specific object. This method serves to ensure that the thinking activity is in a rhythm until a certain topic is deeply and

thoroughly mastered by the students. The cluster method is a well-thoughtout strategy that can be used with students individually or in groups. The method is expressed in the form of a set of ideas expressed by students in group-based activities. This makes it possible to generalize the ideas put forward and find connections between them.

3. THE FOURTH (FIFTH, SIXTH) REDUNDANT METHOD

This method is especially important in helping students develop logical thinking skills. When using it, the following actions are performed:

- the formation of a system of concepts that serve to reveal the essence of the studied topic;
- to achieve the location of four (five, six ...,) concepts related to the topic from the resulting system;
- assign students the task of identifying a concept that is not relevant to the topic, and removing it from the system;
- Students should be encouraged to comment on the nature of their actions. Demonstrates a logical connection between concepts that illuminate the essence of the topic, develops the ability to justify, to justify personal approaches, as well as to compare the opinions of peers with personal opinions.

4. THE "VIDEO PUZZLE" METHOD

In recent years, in pedagogical activities, special attention is paid to the organization of the educational process using various media (computer, telephone, radio, television, slides, video and audiotape). Teachers are faced with the task of appropriate and purposeful use of various media in the educational process.

When using the "video puzzle" method, the following actions are performed:

- students watch several videos that help to illustrate the essence of the subject;
- students explain what process is reflected in each sheet;
- record the essence of the process in notebooks;
- answer questions asked by the teacher.

5. "I KNOW, I WANT TO KNOW, I KNOW" METHOD

This method allows students to assess their level of knowledge on specific topics. Group or group work with students is possible during the usage of the method. In group work, at the end of the lesson, the activities performed by each group are analyzed. The activities of the groups can be organized in the following way:

1. Each group performs the tasks given by the teacher on the basis of the general scheme, and at the end of the lesson the relations of the groups are summarized on the project items;
2. The groups perform the tasks given by the teacher on separate points of the general scheme;

Learning activities are reflected directly in the following scheme, which is reflected on the blackboard or worksheet:

The method is used in 3 stages:

1. The level of students' knowledge of the topic on which the study is planned is determined.
2. The needs of students to enrich their existing knowledge on the topic are studied.
3. Students will be introduced to the topic in detail.

The full details of the steps taken are as follows:

- students are attached to groups;

- the level of students' understanding of a new topic is studied;
- enrichment of students' existing knowledge on a new topic;
- new concepts learned by students are identified;
- at the end of the training a single project will be created.

In conclusion, it should be noted that every teacher and educator who is able to use this type of interactive methods in modern pedagogical education will have the following opportunities:

- develops students' thinking skills;
- the teacher is guaranteed to achieve educational goals;
- students are directed to discussion, debate, discussion;
- free thought prevails;
- provides conscious and creative activity;
- time is used efficiently;
- Positive motives for learning activities are formed for the development of critical thinking and communicative competence.

References

1. Ishmuhammedov R.J. Innovatsion texnologiyalar yordamida ta'lim samaradorligini oshirish omillari. T. 2004-yil
2. Djamilova va O.U.Xasanboeva "Pedagogika fanlarini o'qitish metodikasi" . T. 2009-yil
3. Davletshin M.G. Zamonaviy maktab o'qituvchisining psixalogiyasi. - T.: O'zbekiston, 1999-yil
4. Yo'ldoshev J.G', Hasanov S. "Pedagogik texnologiyalar. O'quv qo'llanma. - T.: Iqtisod-moliya, 2010-yil
5. www.pedagog.uz
6. [www. Ziyonet. uz](http://www.Ziyonet.uz)